

Online repository

PerSpecML: A Perspective-based Approach for Specifying Machine Learning-Enabled Systems

In this online repository, we provide all the material involved in our work including the evaluations (validation in academia, static validation and dynamic validation). For instance, here you can find the participants' characterizations, transcriptions, questionnaires, the final version of the artifacts that comprise PerSpecML (ML task and concern diagram + ML specification template), and details of the relationship between concerns.

The description of the files is below

Academic Validation

Filename	Description
ACAD_Specification_Assignment.pdf	ML-Enabled System Specification Assignment used in the context of in the of two courses on SE for data science.
ACAD_Catalogue_of_Concerns.png	Catalog of concerns used in the academic validation
ACAD_FollowUp-Questionnaire.pdf	Follow-up questionnaire used in the academic validation to get feedback of the participants.

Static Validation

Filename	Description
STATIC_Candidate_Solution.png	Candidate solution for specifying ML-enabled systems.
STATIC_Characterization_Questionnaire.pdf	Characterization questionnaire used in the static validation.
STATIC_Specification_Project_A.png	Retroactively specification for Project A involved in the static validation
STATIC_Specification_Project_B.png	Retroactively specification for Project B involved in the static validation
STATIC_FollowUp_Questionnaire.pdf	Follow-up questionnaire used in the static validation to get feedback of the participants.
STATIC_Transcription.pdf	Transcription of the focus group involved in the static validation.

Dynamic Validation

Filename	Description
DYNAMIC_FollowUp_Questionnaire.pdf	Follow-up questionnaire used in the dynamic validation to get feedback of the participants.
DYNAMIC_Transcription.pdf	Transcription of the two sessions involved in the dynamic validation.
https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPiQXg7E#!/?share_link_id=528545965500	Specifications for <i>Product Classification</i> Project and <i>Market</i> Project using PerSpecML.

Final version of the artifacts

Filename	Description
FINAL_Artifacts_PerSpecML.pdf	Final version of the catalog of perspectives and concerns, how to apply PerSpecML, the Perspective-Based ML Taks and Concern Diagram, the Perspective-Based ML Specification Template, and the relationship between concerns.